

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TEACHER'S ACTIVITY IN SPECIALIZED PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: This article contains comments on the theoretical features of the organization of the educational process in specialized pre-school educational institutions.

Key words: Educational system, specialized pre-school, educational institution, educator.

The methods of upbringing should be understood as the method of influencing the mind, emotions, will, behavior and relations of the child in order to form a well-rounded personality. Methods of education in a specialized preschool education organization do not consist only of influencing children. Education is a two-way process that combines the activity of the educator with the activity of the student. In order to achieve the child's active readiness for educational influence, it is necessary to put him in the right conditions, to organize his active movement. Therefore, organizational forms of education in the science of pedagogy are considered to be ways of organizing collective and individual activities of students in accordance with the pedagogical point of view. Mornings, conversations, work with children in residences can be called organizational forms of education. Methodical ways of purposeful organization of solving one or other educational tasks are called educational tools. Objects used in educational work with children (visual aids, books, radio, television) and activities involving children can be educational tools. Movies, works of art, lively words of a teacher, children's games, community, physical education and amateur clubs serve as educational tools. The result of education depends on the skillful use of methods, tools, and forms of organizing the educational process and their combination.

The effectiveness and driving force of educational methods in specialized preschool education organization depends on the individual-typological characteristics of mentally retarded children and the level of education, as well as the nature of the specific pedagogical situation in which the child lives. The implementation of the educational method will be successful if it corresponds to the leading type of activity of a child of a certain age, mental and physical condition of children. In Arnald, the methods of upbringing are more complicated and sometimes appear in a conflicting relationship. Undoubtedly, a particular method can be used in isolation from other methods of education, but it must interact with other methods.

The tutor teaches the students how to behave in the street and how to behave with their peers. In addition to the explanation, the educator teaches them to get up without knocking on the table to greet the educator, director and other adults, to follow the order in the workplace, to address the educator, the educator, etc. The development and characteristics of children who come to a specialized preschool education organization are diverse. Some of them understand what the teacher says, quickly fulfill his request to all the students, and work diligently on assignments. And some of them do not listen well to the teacher's speech, do not understand, do not immediately understand the teacher's appeal to all the students. In a specialized preschool, children especially like to be encouraged. From the first days, the

teacher praises some of the students for their good behavior, and explains to others that they should listen carefully. In this way, in the process of educating children with mental retardation, the educator in the specialized preschool education organization uses various methods and ways of influence, takes into account the individual characteristics and levels of education of mentally retarded children, the nature of the pedagogical situation, which means that some children and the specialized preschool in general demands to come to any solutions in the interest of the organization.

In order to facilitate learning and formation of skills and competences of using educational methods in practical work with pupils in a specialized pre-school educational organization, they can be conditionally combined into several groups. In the specialized preschool educational organization, methods of forming the consciousness of the students, ways of forming public behavior, motivational methods and self-education methods are also used. It is worth mentioning that in some literature, the methods of education mentioned above are described in a different way, sometimes in terms of content. In order to form a system of worldview and beliefs in the specialized pre-school educational organization, the methods of comprehensive influence on the consciousness, feelings and will of the pupils are included in the methods of education. The essence of this category of methods is that by means of them, the demands applied by the society to the young generation are conveyed to the child's mind. When raising children in a specialized preschool educational organization, the teacher-educator should form the habit of correct behavior at the table, on the street, in dealing with adults, to enjoy this treatment, to form a feeling of satisfaction from the praise of adults for good behavior. pays more attention. In specialized preschool educational organization, explanation in lower classes is a widely used method of belief formation.

The purpose of the explanation is to help the child to reveal the social, spiritual, and aesthetic content of one or another requirement in relation to actions, events, and events, to help him form a correct assessment of behavior and human relations. In specialized pre-school educational organization, the teacher's and educator's lively words have always been and remain influential in the ideological and spiritual formation of the child's personality. Conversations with educational content in different contexts: about the behavior of people in an ethical society); aesthetic (about the beauty of surrounding events, human relations and behavior); it can be political-educational. One of the main, leading methods of education is education by example.

When a primary school student tries to grow up, he tries to imitate adults, people he respects. There are various reasons behind imitation. In particular, their lack of life experiences, lack of stable habits of behavior is also a reason for imitation. As age increases, the level of imitation increases. Sometimes in a specialized pre-school education organization, violators of order, their rudeness, obstinacy, false courage attract the attention of some children. It is not always possible to distinguish mentally retarded children from bad examples. In order to be successful in education, it is necessary to organize the child's life in the family and at school in such a way that it does not become boring, meaningless, and obligatory for him, and it is necessary to teach mentally retarded children to refrain from bad deeds and to resist them.

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